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Study of Seven Common Erection & Commissioning Errors in Instrumentation

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Abstract This paper discusses about "Study of Seven Common Erection & Commissioning Errors in Instrumentation". The instrumentation engineers often make mistakes while working in such system. Here we will see some common mistakes while selecting any instruments (transmitter, switches, control valve, analyzer etc) for its installation in the field. Today smart transmitters or sensor are very fast, accurate & having precise measuring system rather than old, rugged transmitters with the help of new field bus technology. Process variable control, error analysis its reduction, and feedback control is now more accurate with the help of today's modern smart type field bus sensors. Calibration of sensor is the most significant & valuable process which leads to give an error free data to controller for further process in automation system. Here we will see the common mistakes done during erection & commissioning of a flow transmitter with orifice as its primary sensing element.

1. Introduction

In the recent years instrumentation & automation system become a boon for heavy industries, which makes the process easier. This can be achieved by sophisticated instruments like transmitter, field switches, control valves, analysers, relays, PLC, DCS, and SCADA (supervisory control and data acquisition).

To achieve a truthful result correct selection of various instruments are uttermost thing, failing which may leads to a hopeless result in process plants. The sensors like pressure, flow, level, temperature, weight, humidity, acceleration, vibration, speed etc are the primary sensing element for various process points according to their process application. Here we have taken the case of flow measurement. In the case of selecting a flow transmitter with is primary sensing element as an orifice plate has its own principle of operation following Bernoulli's law.

For calibration of such transmitter before installation HART communicator plays an important role. The various data inputs, change of various factors as well as zero trimming can be easily achieved by type of calibrator. Proper earthing of transmitter plays a vital role for safety and error free reading. It is very necessary to check the minor faults before taking any process instrument online, failing which may leads to physical damage, production losses.

The application of orifice flow meter comes into existence in the year of 1779 by an Italian physicist G.B. Venturi. This is the most common meter used for fluid flow measurement. The measurement accuracy is consistently better than +/- 1%. Working mistakes leads to error & if error is higher than +/- 1% then checking is obvious in fluid flow condition, fatigue in secondary device and other physical property of the fluid .So, keeping above criteria in mind one must be careful while installing a new flow transmitter with orifice as a primary sensing element.

2. Mistake # 1: Selecting the Wrong Environment

Before we approach for the installation of flow transmitter, we always need to study the environmental condition to increase the life of sensor as well as to get an error free result corresponding to our process system.

Few common things which we must remember those are: Ambient temperature, humidity, dust contamination, and high voltage directives. These factor which affect the performance of transmitter often overlook by instrumentation engineer and leads to a major common mistake, which are explained below.

2.1. Ambient Temperature

Measurement of temperature is vital parts of nearly all electronic components system designs. Make sure that the sensor components do not to affect their functionality by un-necessary heat up & make the system practically hardly workable.

We must establish some baseline temperature conditions, then figure out through modeling, calculations, simulation, and ultimately measurements – how much will things heat up above that temperature.

The interesting thing is that while it is a very common term, there seem to be different assumptions on what “ambient temperature” really means. Here are some interpretations used by some of us day in and day out, shown in Figure 1 [1].

Figure 1: Ambient Temperature Effect on Sensor Chip

- The temperature of the system, unaffected by the temperature rise of the system itself (either far enough away or before the system is turned on). The equivalent of a true thermal ground.
- The temperature of the air inside the system when it is running. Often measured far away from the component of interest so as not to be too much affected by it.
- The temperature of the air moving over a component.
- The temperature never rises above a certain temperature in case of body or chassis of a system.
- At the entry or exit of the system the temperature of the air driven by fans.
- The temperature of the room when a component or system is tested on the bench, on an evaluation module (EVM) or a real system board (with or without an enclosure).

- g. The temperature setting of the oven when a component or system is tested at high temperature (with or without an enclosure).
- h. The temperature to which a system is preheated for an operational test (of unspecified duration).

2.2. Humidity

Relative humidity (RH) is the one of the vital & noted significant parameter caused by temperature on instruments exposed to open environmental conditions. It is the measure of the amount of holding moisture in the air, expressed in terms of percentage. If the air at a particular temperature contains one third of the water vapor, the relative humidity is 75%. Objects are often made from mixture of two or more materials. The expansion & contraction in materials happens when they attempts to adjust according to environmental condition (change in temperature & humidity).At different relative humidity each material adjust to its equilibrium moisture content (EMC) while they are exposed to water vapor & air.

The three main deterioration often caused by humidity is shown on below Table 1. [2].

Table 1: Humidity Effects on Sensor & Periphery Instruments

Mode	Effects
Dimensional Change	Warping, Dislocation of joints, Splitting, Breaking of fiber, Cracking & Creeping, Loss of surface material
Chemical Reaction	Corrosion of metals, Fading of dyes, weeping or crizzling glass (clouding) , Crystallization & movement of salts , Disintegration & Yellowing of paper
Bio Deterioration	Mould growth (RH 70% or above), Bacterial & Fungi

2.3. Dust Contamination

Air is a mixture of various gases like nitrogen, oxygen, carbon dioxide, argon, and others. Metallic dust particles present in industrial environments cause more troubles in circuits because they're more conductive than typical non industrial dust. Electronic equipment manufacturers often suggest cleaning internal PCBs (printed circuit board) and air filters in products to prevent dust buildup. Below Figure 2, shows a typical PCB effected by prolong dust causing electrical failures. [3].

Figure 2: Dust effect on PCB

2.4. High Voltage Derivatives

The field transmitter or sensors installed nearby any high voltage sources are seen frequently get affected. The high voltage creates an electromagnetic field which affects the internal circuitry of the sensor. A nearby changing magnetic field will influence the distribution of an electric current flowing within an electrical conductor, by electromagnetic induction. When an alternating current (AC) flows through an isolated conductor, it creates an associated alternating magnetic field around it and this alternating magnetic field induces eddy currents in adjacent conductors, and hence alters the overall uniform distribution of current flowing through them. The result is that, the current is concentrated in the areas of the conductor furthest away from nearby conductors carrying current in the same direction.

The value of AC resistance of adjacent conductors increases when compared to its resistance to a DC current. This effect increases with frequency. [4].

3. Mistake # 2: Selecting the Wrong Sensor or Transmitter

Correct selection of sensor plays a vital role in process industry, it is obviously very important to know that what quantity is to be measured in process variables control strategy.

A discrepancy between the sensing technology and the material to be sensed can lead to faulty measurements and severely degraded or lower the control. For an example ,In case of measuring flow rates , all flow meters are designed to measure the rate at which a gas or liquid has been passing through a particular opening section of pipe, but not all flow meters can measure all flows.

One of widely used flow meter is an orifice flow meter installed inside pipe due to easy installation and low cost. However, if flow is not fully developed, the inlet velocity may be distorted and it leads to change local static and total pressure. Another possible problem about orifice flow meter with distorted inlet velocity profile cause early cavitation. The impact of inlet velocity in a local region causes cavitation due to formation of sudden gas bubbles. This will affects the local static and total pressure which may defoliate the integrity of selected orifice flow meter. [5-6].

An orifice flow meter can be selected based upon the type & quantity of process material. The types of orifices are concentric, eccentric, segmental, quadrant, counter, restriction, but for measurement of downstream flow of viscous liquid & gases one must select concentric type orifice instead of other types. Thus the vena-contract is the point in a fluid stream where the diameter of the stream is the least, and fluid velocity is at its maximum, such as in the case of a stream issuing out of a nozzle, (orifice). The maximum contraction takes place at a section slightly downstream of the orifice, where the jet is more or less horizontal. Due to the free jet and the sudden diameter change across orifice edge, the fluid streamlines cannot abruptly changes its specified direction and are unable to closely follow the sharp angle in the tank or pipe wall. The converging streamlines follow a smooth path, which results in the narrowing of the jet (or primary pipe flow) being noticed. The detailed orifice set up with flow directions is shown in below Figure 3.

In a close loop flow measurement system the selection of wrong flow meter may cause the controller to throttle back the flow rate more than it required, obstructing the defined volume of fluid material from reaching the downstream flow process. While selecting an orifice place the following points always to be noted.

3.1. Coefficient of Contraction

It is the factor when the flowing fluid passes the area of the jet at vena contracta to that of proposed orifice. $C_c = \text{Area at vena contracta} / \text{Area of orifice}$. The typical value may be taken as 0.64 for a sharp orifice (concentric with the flow channel). The smaller value of vena contracta has low pressure loss effect at vena taps. [7].

3.2. Reynolds Numbers

It is used to determine the point at which the flow goes from the viscous to turbulent stage. As the flow changes from viscous to turbulent and vice versa, there is a very marked change in the value of the flow coefficient, but there is very little change with further increase in speed. If very high degrees of accuracies are desired when head flow meters are employed, then correction will have to be made for the Reynolds number [8].

Reynolds equation is given by, $R = VD\rho / \mu$, Where: R = Reynolds number, V = average velocity, D = inside pipe diameter, ρ = density of flowing fluid, μ = absolute viscosity.

Laminar and turbulent are two know flow types which normally encountered in liquid flow Measurement operations. Turbulent flow = R is above 3000. Viscous liquids (laminar flow) = R is below 2000. The transition region between the two defined levels may be either laminar or turbulent.

Figure 3: Schematic Diagram of Orifice Flow Meter

In case of selection of wrong transmitter leads to faulty measurement and severely degrade control. To overcome from this situations transmitter in which corrections are applied to the primary sensor signal, using microprocessor to process information which is embedded in memory, or those in which a microprocessor is used in conjunction with a secondary sensor to derive the corrections for the primary sensor signal.

Therefore smart transmitter correct the non-linearity errors of the primary sensor (orifice) through interpolation of calibration data held in memory, or to compensate for the effect of secondary influences on the primary sensor by incorporating a secondary sensor adjacent to primary sensor and interpolating stored calibration data for both the primary and secondary sensors [8].

4. Mistake # 3: Wrong Installation of Sensor or Transmitter

Installation of sensor or transmitter play a vital role in process industry, the best sensor can yield disappointing result if not installed correctly. [6].

Orifice, for example tends to play noisy signal if the flow they are measuring is turbulent. Bends, junction & valve in a pipe can all cause turbulence, thus orifice gives the best results when installed in straight run pipe.

The instrumentation engineer sometimes overlooks the following correct installation which may cause faulty measurement of flow materials.

- a. An orifice must be installed only on a straight pipe section irrespective of the position of pipe section in space.
- b. When selecting a spot for an orifice, one must bear in mind that the flow must fully fill the entire cross section of the pipe.
- c. The orifice plate must be correctly installed in respect to flow direction, the sharp edge of the orifice must face upstream and the bevel side in downstream (flow direction is indicated by arrow. Below Figure 4 & Figure 5, show the difference between proper & improper installation of orifice plate.
- d. Connecting pipes through static pressure tapped upstream and downstream the orifice is transmitted to the meter body must be laid along the shortest distance in a vertical position or with a minimum slope of 1: 10 to horizontal.
- e. To avoid lag in flow meter response, it is recommended to employ connecting pipes not less than 12mm in diameter.
- f. After connecting pipes are installed, joints must be checked for tightness with the aid of soap solution (soap bubbles form in non-tight spots).
- g. When measuring hot materials flow, the transmitter must be placed at a distance above 6m from the orifice plate.

- h. Transmitter Range (LRV-lower range value & URV-upper range value), Damping factor, Unit selection, Transfer Function, Alarm set points, Measurement type etc. must be put correctly by mean of HART communicator.
- i. Sealing pots must be mounted properly in order to protect transmitter from corrosive material flow.

Figure 4: Correct Installation of Orifice - Sharp Edge Facing Upstream

Figure 5: Wrong Installation of Orifice -Sharp Edge Facing Downstream

- j. For miscellaneous analog signal measurement correct signal transmission is required. The ground based telemetry includes two wires 4-20 mA dc signals. Both power and signal are being carried over the same pair of wires. The current signal deteriorates less in long run cable irrespective of its internal circuit resistance and number of connection. It is also identified as a live zero signal due to its selection of zero value as 4mA.
- k. Route the impulse piping so that no deposits can accumulate. Angles of inclination should not be less than 8 % ascending or descending, see Figure 6 below.

Figure 6: Hook Up Diagram of Seal Pot & Connecting Pipes Mounting

- I. Two-wire transmitters must have 12Vdc minimum voltage at the terminals in order to operate. But in industrial cases we may use 24Vdc which leaves a 12Vdc voltage drop across the loop. Applying ohm's law in terms of resistance $R=E/I$, Where R is the resistance of circuit, E=Potential across the circuit and I= Current flowing in the circuit, and taking standard higher range analog current signal as 20mA or 0.02 Amps; we can compute the maximum resistance allowed in the loop: $R = E/I = 12 \text{ Vdc} / 0.02 \text{ A} = 600 \text{ Ohms}$. See Figure 7 below.

Figure 7: Load Loop Capacity

To derive the total loop resistance we add: 250 Ohms Typical Load Resistor + 45 Ohms Line Resistance (varies with length and size) +70 Ohms Surge Protector = 365 Ohms Total Loop Resistance (Loop Load).

This loop will operate satisfactorily having a 235 Ohm surplus load capability. (600 - 365 = 235 Ohms).

5. Mistake # 4: Improper Earthing /Grounding

A common reference potential determined as a zero voltage is known as common ground, it is the return path from power supply to all circuit in the network. Proper and correct grounding is an essential procedure for safely and reliably operating electrical and instrumentation systems. Earth pit plays a vital role in instrumentation process system. It reflects the idea of proper grounding of electrical and instrument equipment's for low, medium and high voltages. The grounding practices here are intended for the instrument that operates below 60Vdc.

The concepts of dirty and clean grounds are the AC and DC grounds, DC grounds usually relate SLC, PLC, DCS, and other metering and controlling equipment.

The main purpose of proper earthing is for safety, over voltage protection and voltage stabilization, the earthing are often seems to be either plate type (Cast iron, Galvanized iron, copper) or pipe type (usually Galvanized iron). So, to over-ride the improper earthing/grounding, for more than one system it is often recommended the star ground connection. This is the most effective way of avoiding ground loops by means of separate ground return with respect to the power supply [9].The proper grounding bed techniques is shown in below Figure 8.

Figure 8: Schematic View of Grounding Types

Moreover it's generally a best practice to insulate an instrument sensor from the thermodynamic effects of its surroundings. The most common electrical problems due to poor installation are ground loops. Ground loops occur when avalanche current flows through the instrumentation wiring between two points that are supposed to be at the same potential, but aren't. The resulting electrical interference can cause random fluctuations in the sensors' output and may even cause damage to the sensors themselves.

A master grounding point can isolate the plant's instrument from ground loop current if connected in series. at the entry or exit of the system Else, the plant should have a grid grounding point and all of its points are at the same electrical point. Potential imbalance will be happen in case of faulty connection and insufficient wires between ground loops and grid.

Figure 9: Schematic Diagram of Poor Grounding

Instruments must be grounded to provide a reference voltage for the data signals they generate. Relying on earth ground is risky since not all of the earth shares the same electrical potential. The resulting currents will interfere with the sensors' signals [10]. The above Figure 9 is the schematic of poor grounding technique.

6. Mistake # 5: Wrong Calibration

Calibration of sensor / transmitter plays a vital role in process industry. The magnitude of error and consequently the correction to be applied is determined by making a periodic comparison of the instrument with standards which are known to be constant. The entire procedure laid down for making, adjusting, or checking a scale so that readings of an instrument or measurement system conform to an accepted standard. To avoid wrong calibration the following points and observations need consideration [11-12].

- a. Calibration of the instrument is carried out with the instrument in the same position (upright, horizontal etc.) and subjected to the same temperature and other environmental conditions under which it is to operate while in service.
- b. The instrument is calibrated with values of the measured impressed both in the increasing and in the decreasing order.
- c. Output readings for a series of impressed values going up the scale may not agree with the output readings for the same input values when going down.
- d. Lines or curves plotted in the graph may or may not close form a loop.
- e. Calibrating an instrument without a precision NABL (National Accreditation Board for Testing and Calibration Laboratories) accredited master calibrator.

HART (highway addressable remote transducer) is a digital protocol designed for configuring transmitters. Most 'smart' transmitters are HART compatible which requires the use of either a handheld HART communicator or

Windows software and a HART modem to access the configuration parameters. Configuring a transmitter with HART requires that the transmitter be powered up, and does not require a source.

Most instrumentation engineers know that a sensor/transmitter must be calibrated in order to associate a numerical value with the electrical signal coming out of the transmitter. Yet all too often, the instruments are calibrated just once during installation then left to operate unattended for years. The result is an insidious problem known as drift. A sensor's output tends to creep higher and higher (or lower and lower), even if the measured variable hasn't changed. Deposition on the sensing surfaces, corrosion in the wiring, and long term wear on moving parts can all cause an instrument to begin generating artificially high (or low) readings. As a result, the controller will gradually increase or decrease its control efforts to compensate for a non-existent error. Drift can be reduced by proper choice of sensing technology. And even when drift cannot be eliminated, recalibrating every sensor in the plant at intervals recommended by their manufacturers can accommodate it. Unfortunately, project engineers are often so anxious to finish a job and get on with operating the process that they neglect such basic maintenance. Arguably the most challenging sources of drift are those that vary over time. Deteriorating probes and moving parts beginning to wear out can slowly change an instrument's accuracy. So, maintenance calibration is required periodically even if there are no known issues with the instrument.

7. Mistake # 6: Overlook Minor Faults

Often instrumentation engineer are so over confident or do hurry in selection, installation, calibration of instruments, may cause overlook minor faults which may leads to a huge error. The following points are necessary to keep in mind while working with an instrumentation system.

- a. Check that wires are properly connected & tightened to transmitter & other controller.
- b. Check the IJB (instrumentation junction box) terminal block and make sure that wires continuity, tightness & dust free contact.
- c. Be sure that no leakages are there in tubing area including manifold, bends, drain valves etc.
- d. There should not be any naked or cut part in signal cable.
- e. Always use proper selection in multi meter while measuring current, voltage, resistance etc; else it may damage transmitter or other sophisticated equipment.
- f. Always check the accuracy & precision of instrument reading don't allow the approx reading more than its allowable range.
- g. Checking for zero suppression and zero elevation for sensor during installation.

8. Mistake # 7: Relinquish Soon

It is seen that some instrumentation engineer are often so anxious to finish a job and get on with operating the process that the neglect such basic settings and maintenance which may lead to a wrong display of value or readings, which is very disappointing. Below points will clear the idea about the quick relinquish from work.

- a. Hurriedness in work leads to wrong results.
- b. Carelessness in work leads to wrong setup or installation.
- c. Expertise or work knowledge in a particular equipment/instruments is essential, failure of which may leads to false setup or readings.
- d. Carefully follow the instruction of operating manuals before start working on any equipment/instrument and not to create your own setup which may leads to faulty reading or permanently failure of process equipment/instrument.
- e. While calibrating an equipment / instrument repeated calibration is needed to get the accurate & precise readings, most instrumentation engineer lost patience which result in wrong or incomplete calibration.

9. Conclusion

Instrumentation Engineering brought a revolution in the process industry at late 1970s. Various measurements are done in industries by process automation system and proper ideas and technical knowledge are the key factor for an error free setup. While designing, selecting, erecting and commissioning any flow measurement sensor we must be careful and active enough such that no errors shall take place while connecting it to the process. Keeping above points in mind we can eliminate or minimize the errors, often did by the instrumentation engineers at their work place.

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